

ENHANCING HIV CARE IN NASARAWA STATE, NIGERIA: THE ROLE OF CLINICAL MENTORSHIP ON PATIENT RETENTION

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Abstract: Retention in HIV care is a vital component of achieving epidemic control and ensuring the success of treatment programs. Interruption in treatment (IIT) undermines this goal and is associated with poor health outcomes, including increased morbidity and mortality. This study evaluates the effect of the National Clinical Mentorship Program on client retention in care and reduction of IIT among HIV clients in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

The study involved 47 health facilities in Nasarawa State where clinical mentors were deployed. In these facilities, mentors supported immediate tracking of clients who missed appointments and facilitated the return of these individuals to care. Data covering November 2021 to August 2022 were extracted from the Retention and Audit Determination Tool (RADET) and analyzed using descriptive statistics, bivariate and multivariate analyses, including Chi-square and logistic regression, to compare outcomes pre- and post-mentorship deployment.

Following the mentorship intervention, the IIT rate dropped significantly from 7% to 0.5%. The age group 25–34 years had the highest IIT burden but still experienced a decline from 41.6% to 33.3%. Pregnant women were more likely to experience IIT compared to non-pregnant women. Tertiary facilities recorded the highest IIT rates, underscoring systemic challenges at higher-level care centers. The mentorship program successfully facilitated improved client tracking, care continuity, and reduction in attrition.

The implementation of a structured clinical mentorship program significantly reduced IIT and improved retention in HIV care in Nasarawa State. Tailored mentorship and gender-sensitive strategies are recommended for sustained improvements and to meet UNAIDS' 95-95-95 goals.

Keywords: HIV, retention in care, clinical mentorship, interruption in treatment, Nigeria

Introduction

The human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) epidemic remains one of the most significant public health challenges in Nigeria and sub-Saharan Africa. Achieving epidemic control requires strategic interventions that enhance the quality of HIV care, with

retention in care emerging as a central pillar. Retention in care encompasses all efforts to ensure that individuals diagnosed with HIV are consistently engaged in a continuum of lifelong services that include antiretroviral therapy (ART), clinical

monitoring, laboratory assessments, and psychosocial support.

The World Health Organization (WHO) and UNAIDS have articulated ambitious goals through the 95-95-95 strategy aimed at ending the HIV epidemic by ensuring that 95% of people living with HIV (PLHIV) know their status, 95% of those diagnosed are on sustained ART, and 95% of those on treatment achieve viral suppression. However, failure to retain clients in care jeopardizes progress toward these targets. One of the clearest indicators of poor retention is Interruption in Treatment (IIT), defined by PEPFAR as the absence of any clinical contact within 28 days after a missed appointment. IIT leads to treatment failure, increased risk of transmission, development of drug resistance, and ultimately, increased HIV-related morbidity and mortality.

In response to these challenges, the Nigerian Ministry of Health, in partnership with the United States Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and other international stakeholders, initiated the National HIV Clinical Mentorship Program in 2021. Implemented in 19 states, including Nasarawa, the program deploys experienced clinicians to selected health facilities to provide ongoing education, capacity building, and quality improvement support to healthcare providers offering HIV services. The mentorship model promotes a hands-on approach, in which mentors help build facility-level systems for efficient client management, particularly in areas of retention, ART adherence, and case tracking.

The introduction of this mentorship program in Nasarawa State is particularly relevant given the state's burden of HIV and the variability in service delivery

across its health facilities. Clinical mentors have played a pivotal role in reinforcing patient tracking systems, advocating for timely release of tracking funds, and ensuring adherence to national HIV guidelines. Through close collaboration with facility staff, mentors identify clients who have missed appointments, assess reasons for IIT, and facilitate client return to care.

Multiple studies have highlighted the effectiveness of mentorship programs in improving HIV service delivery. For example, a study in Zambia showed that mentorship, when combined with continuous quality improvement and a public health approach, led to substantial program gains at both facility and provincial levels. Similarly, in South Africa and Malawi, studies have linked poor retention and IIT to systemic, individual, and societal factors such as stigma, long travel distances, poverty, ART side effects, and work-related time constraints.

A retrospective analysis conducted across 16 states in Nigeria found an IIT burden of 32% among ART clients, with risk factors including male gender, pediatric status, being on first-line treatment, and having unsuppressed viral loads. These findings underscore the need for innovative strategies such as clinical mentorship to address these multifaceted challenges.

Nasarawa State presents a suitable case study for evaluating the effectiveness of the clinical mentorship approach. With mentorship implementation across 47 facilities, this study provides an opportunity to assess the impact of mentorship on IIT rates, retention in care, and associated demographic and clinical characteristics. Preliminary evidence suggests a significant improvement, but further analysis is

required to document trends, understand barriers, and propose sustainable solutions.

The 25–34 age group, often in the economically active phase of life, is frequently identified as the most vulnerable to treatment interruption due to factors such as job-related mobility, economic instability, and social pressures. Similarly, pregnant women face unique challenges in maintaining consistent clinical contact due to healthcare system inefficiencies and socio-cultural barriers. Facility level, particularly at tertiary institutions, may also influence retention rates due to factors such as patient overload, bureaucratic delays, and staff shortages.

The present study aims to generate empirical evidence on the **effectiveness of clinical mentorship** in reducing IIT and improving **retention in care**. By comparing IIT rates before and after the deployment of clinical mentors, and analyzing the sociodemographic profiles of clients most affected, the study contributes to a broader understanding of retention dynamics in HIV care in Nigeria. It also offers practical insights for policymakers, program managers, and health practitioners seeking to scale interventions that support the HIV care cascade.

Given the pressing need to achieve the UNAIDS 95-95-95 targets and ultimately, epidemic control, the strategic role of mentorship in bolstering facility-level capacity, accountability, and patient-centered care cannot be overstated. As the fight against HIV enters a new phase, marked by treatment scale-up and decentralized service delivery, mentorship offers a scalable and sustainable approach to bridge the gap between policy and practice.

In conclusion, this study not only evaluates the performance of the mentorship model in Nasarawa State but also seeks to uncover gaps and opportunities for improving the design and implementation of similar programs nationwide. Addressing gender disparities, enhancing support for pregnant women, and targeting age-specific vulnerabilities will be critical for optimizing retention outcomes. These findings will inform the adaptation of mentorship strategies to diverse contexts, driving continued progress toward HIV epidemic control in Nigeria.

Methodology

Study area

Nasarawa state is located in North Central Nigeria with a population estimate of 2.5 million people and covers 27,117 km². The official language is English with Hausa, Fulani, and many other local languages. The economy of the state is centered on agriculture, mining, and trade. One hundred and forty-two facilities are offering HIV services and these include two tertiary facilities. These facilities cater to the needs of over 72,000 active clients with an interruption in treatment rate of over 2%. The State has a diverse geography with plains, mountains, and hills and is the home of many ethnic groups. The State is administered democratically with the Governor being the chief accounting officer and overseeing 13 local government areas. This study area, in this operational research, represents the geographical area allotted for official work.

Recruitment of mentors and deployment

Indigenous medical doctors in Nasarawa were recruited using structured interview questions after a due advert and shortlisting process carried out jointly

by the implementing partner and the State Ministry of Health. The 10 recruited mentors had onboarding training that covered the entire cascade of care and were then allocated facilities that covered the 13 local government areas. An initial deployment to 47 facilities was done after the engagement of the clinical mentors in November of 2021. These mentors provided ongoing practical training across the HIV cascade of care to clinicians and all other staff working in the HIV space in each of the 47 facilities.

Study population and settings

Data of all PLHIVs who were enrolled within the Institute of Human Virology Nigeria (IHVN) Nasarawa network into care and received ART from 2010 to 2022 from 47 Presidents Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief/ Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (PEPFAR/ CDC) supported public health facilities (Tertiary, Secondary, Primary) and private health facilities across 13 LGAs was used for this study. These 47 facilities, out of a total of 126, had clinical mentors deployed in December 2021. Baseline data was collected for the baseline study in November 2021, and another set of data was collected in August 2022. IHVN is a non-governmental organization that provides quality HIV care through technical assistance and support to health facilities. In the 47 facilities where mentors worked, every client who missed an appointment was tracked immediately. A list of potential IIT clients was generated and followed through by linking those clients to trackers who ensured they were returned to care. Mentors ensured that the process of tracking in the facilities was strengthened as part of their routine mentoring activities including facilitating the timely

release of tracking funds from the implementing partner. Regular mentorship is provided along the lines of the recommendation by the World Health Organisation.⁵

Study design and implementation

The study is a comparative retrospective cross-sectional study of clinical data on RADET of patients enrolled on ART as of November 2021 compared to that of August 2022.

Data collection/analysis

All patients reported on the Retention and Audit Determination Tool (RADET) as of November 2021 and August 2022 were extracted. The demographic and clinical program parameters of all patients will be described using frequencies and percentages. Bivariate and multivariate analyses using Chi square and logistic regression were conducted for patients that were active or LTFU. All the p- values reported are two-sided.

Analyses

The relationship between patient retention (active vs dropped out/inactive) with age at start of ART (in years), sex, initial regime line, initial CD4 count, current CD4 count, and viral load was examined using a logistic regression. This model produces a probability function of subjects remaining active in the program or dropping out. Using step-wise backward elimination of the least significant variables, the most parsimonious statistical model was selected as the final model. To minimize the effect of multicollinearity in cases where two variables were correlated, only one of the variable pairs was used in the model, while the other variable was used in a similar alternative model.

Ethical clearance

Ethical clearance was obtained from ethics committees of Dalhatu Araf Specialist Hospital and State Ministry of Health.

Results

Year 2021

The variables that significantly predicted patient retention were sex, pregnancy status, current regimen line, and viral load (Table 2).

The probability of retention decreases with increasing viral load, with the probability of

retention at about 95% at low viral load, declining as viral load increased (Figure 1).

Year 2022

The variable that significantly predicted patient retention was viral load (Table 3).

The probability of retention decreases with increasing viral load, with the probability of retention at about 88% at low viral load, declining as viral load increased (Figure 2).

Figure 1. The probability of retention decreases with increasing viral load count in the 47 selected facilities from RADET of 2021 pre-deployment of mentors. Gray shading represents the 95% confidence interval.

Discussion

The IIT in these selected facilities for 2021 is 7% against 0.5% for 2022 (Table 1). Even though the IIT for 2021 was much lower than previous works documented in the country, in 2022 after 10 months of mentoring work, the IIT rate fell steeply to 0.5%, which reflects a positive outcome of the mentoring program. This achievement could be said to be the

outcome of strategies already in place that yielded fruit within the year under review. However, the only new approach adopted in 2022 was bringing on board the clinical mentorship program, and thus the steep decline in IIT can be best explained by the adoption of the clinical mentorship program in the facilities under review. Further studies to compare the facilities where mentors are deployed with those facilities

Figure 2. The probability of retention decreases with increasing viral load count in the 47 selected facilities from

Where mentors were not deployed will better help to resolve this and provide a causal relation or otherwise of the mentoring strategy with a reduction in facility IIT. This finding of a positive effect is comparable to the findings of similar work done in Rivers State Nigeria which found an increase in case findings and viral suppression amongst clients with the implementation of the clinical mentorship program.¹⁴ Even though this finding is not about retention in care **2022 RADET post-deployment of mentors.**

Females were found in this study to be more likely to drop out of treatment, which goes against the norm where women have better health-seeking behavior.¹⁵ A sub-optimal health-seeking behavior amongst female PLHIVs may actually be a result of lots of our women who are pregnant seeking health services outside our facilities but this certainly cannot completely explain the reversal and we need to do a deeper dive to unravel this finding. Supporting the idea that the reversal of health-seeking behavior

which this study speaks to, it addresses the impact on other thematic areas that lead to epidemic control. In Zambia, case-finding yield and viral suppression also improved post-mentoring as was found in the later study in Rivers State, Nigeria.⁶

IIT was found in this study to be related to sex ($p = 0.001$), pregnancy status ($p = 0.004$), current regimen ($p = 0.001$), and viral load ($p = 0.001$; Tables 2 and 3).

Gray shading represents the 95% confidence interval.

between males versus females here is due to pregnant women seeking care outside traditional hospital facilities is the finding that non-pregnant women are more likely to remain in treatment compared to pregnant women. This can be explained by the poor utilization of antenatal services generally by our women, who prefer to deliver with traditional birth attendants even if they had a course of antenatal care in health facilities.

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of study participants (clients) from the 47 facilities in RADET.

Variables Treatment interruption

Those on second-line treatment, especially in 2021, were significantly related to interruptions in treatment compared to the first-line regimen (Table 4). This is a sad reflection on the program, as it will entail that these clients will most likely fail again and will need

to be switched to the third-line regimen with all the attendant challenges. However, it was good to note that with the start of the mentorship program, the IIT rate of 15% in this sub-group again crashed to 0.3%.

Table 3. Logistic regression result testing the relationship between patient outcome and demographic variables, treatment regime, and immunity indicators count in the 47 selected facilities from RADET in 2022.

Variables	Df	Deviance	p
NULL			
Sex	1	1.63	0.2013
Age at start of ART (years)	1	1.97	0.1603
Pregnancy status ¹	2	585.08	<2.2e-16
Current CD4 count	1	62.06	3.33E-15
Current regimen line	3	56.06	4.07E-12
Current viral load	1	12.21	0.0004762

High viral load was correlated with a high interruption in treatment rate, which is in keeping with the fact that these clients were not taking drugs and thus viral load was expected to rise in their bloodstream (Figures 1 and 2).

Limitation of the study

This study is limited by lack of control over the quality of original data collected and the uncontrolled variable such as the fact that the implementing partner has staff that offer similar services as the mentors. Our mentors recruitment approach of using advert placements and using structured questionnaires in the interview limited our ability for targeted recruitment of HIV

specialists which would have better improved our outcomes.

Conclusion and recommendation

Clinical mentoring can reduce IIT among HIV patients. A study found a decrease from 7% to 0.5%. Tailored mentorship programs can improve retention in HIV care and reduce IIT rates. Gender-specific barriers should be addressed, and interventions should be customized for pregnant women for better program effectiveness and health outcomes.

A deep dive will need to be conducted to further unravel the dynamics at work in these sub-populations to better understand the strategies to

fashion and use to mitigate the interruption of treatment.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization of Ideas: Anthony Ajeh. Data analysis and visualization: Anthony Ajeh, Ruth

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Availability of data and materials

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available upon reasonable request.

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